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Arts-Based Educational Research in Action in Vocational Education

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Abstract

This paper argues that there are different ways of understanding and representing the human condition and that all forms of understanding have a frame of reference that enables or constrains the way we think, how we express what we think and what we have learned from experience. Arts Based Educational Research (ABER) is rooted in the potential of the evocative power of aesthetic experience to heighten human vitality (Dewey, 1934, 2005) in ways which have the capacity to enhance not only the practice of education but also the conduct and representation of educational research. This paper presents findings from a qualitative, empirical study which explores teachers' experiences of engaging in University-supported, practitioner-research programme of continuous professional development for teachers of vocational education, informed by key ideas and concepts in the theoretical framework underpinning ABER. Barone and Eisner (2012) draw attention to how ABER is essentially evocative. They argue that utilising the evocative expressive properties of an artistic, aesthetic medium is one of the primary ways in which arts-based research contributes to human understanding. Through the presentation of extracts from a series of 10 case studies accompanied by evaluative commentaries and critical discussion, this paper offers an thematic analysis of teachers' accounts as they attempt to improve their practice in vocational education contexts through direct engagement in ABER. Emerging evidence from a preliminary analysis of the narrative accounts of the experiences of teachers of vocational education as they learn how to be (*savoir être*), systematic, credible and trustworthy practitioner-researchers, suggests that, using the expressive properties of an artistic medium is one of the primary ways in which ABER can contribute to the improvement of educational practice including the conduct and representation of educational research.

Keywords

arts-based educational research, practitioner-research, aesthetic experience, academic writing and scholarship

1 Art as experience

Dewey (2005, p. 19) points out that all human ‘experience is art in germ’, immediate before it is mediated, presentational before it is representational, sensuous before it is symbolic. Eisner (1993) draws attention to how experience is the bedrock upon which meaning is constructed, therefore he argues, the meanings we construct to a large extent depend upon our ability to get in touch with the qualitative world we inhabit. According to Eisner, the arts contribute to the growth of mind in a mind-making process and this involves connecting with the qualitative world of human experience. To create a form of experience that can be regarded as aesthetic, he contends, requires a mind that animates our imaginative capacities and evokes our ability, ‘to undergo emotionally pervaded experience forms of experience that are at once moving and touching, experiences of a consummatory nature, experiences that are treasured for their intrinsic value’ (Eisner 2002, p. xii). He notes how these are experiences which we can access when we attend to the world with an aesthetic frame of reference that interacts with forms of art that make such experience possible. He invites us to consider how the arts can serve as models of what educational aspiration and practice might be at their very best. According to Eisner, when we are able to think about teaching as an artful undertaking and to conceive of learning as having aesthetic features, we can envision the design of an educational environment and the educational experiences which are encountered within that environment, as an artistic task. Works of art call attention to ontological and epistemological aspects of human experience that we sometimes cannot or would prefer not to see or are too great to bear, or too extreme or too complex to be put easily into words. From this standpoint, different forms of understanding are promoted by different forms of representation which may or may not be related to reason and argument rather than intuition and experience. Beliefs about what constitutes legitimate research in education therefore, have enormous ramifications for the understanding, or misunderstanding, of human behaviour, social interaction and educational practice. When the tools we use to represent educational phenomena limit what is expressible or representational, a certain price is paid for the neglect of what has been omitted. This is one of the reasons why the tools we use to represent the world and the human condition (including the world of educational research) need to be capable of making lived experience palpable. ‘We need to touch the souls of students as well as to be able to measure their sleeve length or hat size’ (Barone and Eisner, 2012, p.4).

This paper presents findings from a small-scale, qualitative, empirical study which reports teachers’ experiences of a programme of continuing professional learning and development, including intensive training in educational research, for teachers of vocational education through their engagement in the national Practitioner Research Programme (PRP), funded by the Education and Training Foundation (ETF) and delivered by the University of Sunderland. The PRP has been nationally funded by the Education and Training Foundation (ETF) in England for over 8 years. The purpose of the PRP is to open up collaborative, cooperative research and pedagogic spaces, informed by key ideas and concepts from the theoretical framework underpinning arts-based educational research (ABER) in which teachers of vocational education are encouraged and enabled to improve their practice through systematic, University-supported practitioner research.

Barone and Eisner (2012) note how the power of ABER is that it is essentially evocative. Harnessing the expressive properties of an artistic medium through aesthetic experience, they argue, is one of the most potent ways in which ABER contributes to the development and advancement of human understanding. Extracts from a series of 10 case studies, supported by evaluative commentaries, are analysed, critically discussed and presented in this paper. They offer insights into the experiences of a group of teachers of vocational education as they work together to improve educational practice as part of the PRP. These case study extracts provide practical examples of the power of social, collaborative, cooperative and aesthetic experience

in igniting teacher-imagination, enhancing and increasing human learning, heightening human vitality (Dewey, 1934; 2005) and improving educational practice through University-supported, practitioner-research, in ways which are capable of evoking learning and deepening understanding of complex and enduring educational issues, concepts, theories, in education and educational research conducted in vocational contexts.

In ABER research, the author (in relation to this research study, the teacher-educator) creates and calls upon experiences that would otherwise not be directly available to practitioner-researchers working in the sector. In ABER various perspectives on the meaning of activities are not merely stated and explained but, as is the case of good art, expressed, lived, experienced, and enhanced. Within the literal and visual arts physical realities are recast into a “composed apparition” (Langer, 1957), a virtual whole ... moving away from an everyday world and temporarily entering a new and less familiar one. The apparition of the storied world itself. Engagement in a world beyond the range of our everyday experience becomes a heuristic device (a mental/affective shortcut) that speaks directly to familiar nearby concerns even as it raises questions about them. ABER employs vivid images, stories and descriptions of other perspectives of the real-world to encourage and support the development of teachers’ capacities and confidence in engaging in educational research, their development of scholarship and the improvement of educational practice. Barone and Eisner (2012) point to how ABER has the capacity to trigger empathy and bring us closer together in ways which, in the context of this research, enable practitioner-researchers in vocational education to rethink entrenched pedagogic practice including competing ideas about educational research and the implementation of educational policy by challenging taken-for-granted assumptions (their own and those of others) in the light of experience.

ABER plays by rules that differ from those applied to more conventional educational research. For example, ABER may be judged, firstly by its illuminating effects including its ability to reveal what had not been noticed previously. Secondly ABER has the ability to make vivid subtle but significant aspects of the educational world that the research in question addresses, encouraging and enabling the reader/viewer/listener to notice or become more aware of what they had not been aware of or noticed before. In other words ABER invites reader/viewer/listener into the research experience,

When I disclose what I have seen, my results invite other researchers to look where I did and see what I saw. My ideas are candidates for others to entertain, not necessarily as truth, let alone Truth, but as positions about the nature and meaning of a phenomenon that may fit their sensibility and shape their thinking about their own inquiries’

Peshkin 1985, p. 8

Following Peshkin, ABER invites the reader/viewer/listener to look where the researcher looked and to see what they saw, through a constellation of evocative factors expressed and represented in an artistic image. In addition, ABER has the capacity to generate questions which have not yet been asked. ABER also provides opportunities to focus incisively upon educationally salient issues and enduring questions where the material helps us to get to the heart of the matter, persuading readers of the educational importance of events portrayed. Finally, ABER’s has the ability to make reference to phenomena outside of the research text which enables the reader/viewer/listener to make connections that had not been made previously. ABER puts literary language to work by employing language designed to stimulate imaginative faculties which bring the reader/viewer/listener into presence, inviting them into the direct experience of another person/world of ideas. ABER does not tend to use direct and denotative language. Instead, it employs the language of the:

- Evocative
- Expressive
- Contextual
- Connotative
- Vernacular

2 Research methodology

The methodology employed in this research is inductive beginning with individual cases in order to tentatively and incrementally move toward what may be more general. Thematic analysis is used to identify recurring themes in data from 10 case studies and narrative accounts of practitioners engaged in the national PRP.

The PRP purposefully employs ABER in bringing complex ideas and concepts in education and educational research to life. The lived experiences of teachers conducting research in the PRP are used to illustrate the impact of ABER upon education practice. The research problem which provides the impetus for this study aims to address a number of research questions. How best to support teachers in helping them to research and improve their practice through systematic, supported practitioner-research? How aesthetic experience and the arts can contribute to making complex ideas and concepts in educational research accessible and useful to teachers and education leaders working in vocational contexts? It also attempts to address the research question of, how intensive University-supported intensive research training can contribute to increasing the vocational education sector's capacity for self-improvement through systematic practitioner-research conducted and reported in ways which also meet the standards necessary to rise to the requirements of successful peer-review and publication? Finally, the question of, if/how the use of visual and other forms of art, can mediate the acquisition and development of teachers' understanding of ideas, theories, concepts in educational research and practice in vocational education is also explored.

Rethinking the relationship between teachers, researchers, students, education leaders and others and building their capacities to conduct research together for mutual benefit in the interests of the common good will be pivotal in the development of new pedagogical principles and practices and the opening up of places and spaces in which we can imagine new and inclusive educational futures for all learners. Our purpose in calling for a shift in existing educational research practices and horizons which frame the present differently, is to enable teachers to help their learners to encounter existing social, intellectual and economic boundaries and obstacles to their engagement in education and educational research not as prisons or shackles to past exclusion and inequities but as tension points condensing the past in order to imagine and open up new possibilities and relationships in education and educational research for teachers and learners alike.

This brings us to the question of what educational futures are desirable and for whom and sets us on a quest not so much for "what works" as to the question of "education for what?". In systems of education preoccupied with quick-fix responses to hyperactive policy processes conducted at social media speed, measures of educational quality based upon performance outputs have become conflated with educational standards. Questions of educational values and purpose are now being displaced and reduced to blunt and crude measures of outputs which then masquerade as what counts as quality in education. In this context, it is wise to remember that a public that is inured to these fixed ways of seeing and thinking about what we mean by good education, may find it difficult to imagine how educational research and the improvement of educational practice might be done differently. If we accept that education should be respected and concerned with the protection and pursuit of the common good and that the right to quality education which fosters the intellectual, moral and social capacities of all learners

including their abilities to work together and transform the world with empathy, compassion, imagination and care, then we need to create conditions in which their teachers can do the same. This will involve building the capacities of teachers to lay the foundations for flourishing, divergent futures of education as well as finding new approaches to teachers' professional learning and the improvement of research and practice informed by ABER. and aesthetic experience.

A central aim of ABER is to enhance perspectives related to human activities which are educational in character. ABER involves the presence of certain aesthetic qualities or design elements of education which infuse both the process of educational inquiry and the research "text". To date Most existing ABER has employed forms of art that are primarily of a literary nature rather than fine art, music, visual, or performing arts. ABER frames a research field that exists across and beyond disciplines and can also take the form of non-linguistic arts including visual and performing arts. The legitimacy of ABER has been questioned by those who have misunderstood this unique approach to educational enquiry. Much research in vocational education therefore has tended to be framed by an epistemology that seeks certainty and aims to produce findings that are meant to predict and control educational outcomes and in ways which enable consumers of educational research to formulate, prescribe, predict, inspect and control educational practice, research in vocational education. To date, this has tended to encourage many researchers in education to only pursue knowledge that is considered to be objective, valid and reliable by following the conventions and protocols of the natural sciences rather than research grounded in human experience.

The research reported here takes the above published works as starting points. It draws attention to how until relatively recently, the initial and continuing professional development of teachers of vocational education has rarely involved purposive engagement with the arts and humanities. Within the past few decades however, growing numbers of educational scholars and researchers involved in the initial and continuing professional development of teachers of vocational education have begun to explore the possibilities of artistic forms of understanding in the development of the professional learning of teachers of vocational education.

3 Emerging Evidence

While it is too early to draw conclusions from this research, as it is still work-in-progress, emerging evidence from a preliminary thematic analysis of the narrative accounts of the experiences of 10 teachers of vocational education as they learn how to be (*savoir être*) teachers and practitioners researchers through the PRP, suggest that, using the expressive properties of an artistic medium is one of the primary ways in which ABER can contribute to the teaching and conduct of research and practice in vocational education by making theories, concepts, ideas and arguments surrounding methodology, methods, academic writing and scholarship in educational research more accessible and meaningful to sector practitioners. This study is purposefully putting ABER to work through a spectrum of factors expressed and represented in artistic artefacts and aesthetic phenomena to explore if/how the use of visual and other forms of art, can mediate the acquisition and development of teachers' understanding of ideas, theories, concepts in educational research in order to improve educational practice across a range of vocational contexts.

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Biographical Note

I joined the University of Sunderland in 2015, first as an Academic Tutor and then as a Research Assistant for the University of Sunderland's Centre for Excellence in Teacher Training (SUNCETT). My work involves supporting teaching and research as part of a National Practitioner Research Programme (PRP) for teachers and education leaders from the Further, Adult and Vocational Education (FAVE) sector across England. This programme of research support is sponsored by the Education and Training Foundation (ETF). I work in close collaboration with the Foundation in supporting the delivery of the ETF-SUNCETT PRP which leads to the award of a Master of Arts Module or a Master of Philosophy Research Degree. Each year, I support the organisation and management of the Foundation's Annual Research Conference in London.